

Received: 03 Mar 2021/ Accepted: 08 Mar 2021/ Published: 30 April 2021
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4730830>

Clove oil nanoparticles as anti-inflammatory molecules

Neeraja Revi¹, Aravind Kumar Rengan²

¹Department of Biotechnology, Indian Institute of Technology Hyderabad, 502285, India

²Department of Biomedical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Hyderabad, 502285, India

Corresponding author: Aravind Kumar Rengan (aravind.bme@iith.ac.in)

This work was presented at the **International Conference on Biomaterials and Biosensor Technologies** held during 12-13, March 2021 at **Bannari Amman Institute of Technology**

Introduction: Chronic inflammation is considered as a precursor for a multitude of diseases like neurodegenerative disorders, cancer, cardiac disorders etc. Non-Steroid Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) are one of the existing treatment methods to reduce inflammation. However, they are known to cause side effects like gastro-intestinal ulcers and stomach bleedings due to their non-selective activity on COX enzymes. Dietary inclusion of polyphenols has reportedly reduced inflammation and associated disorders, especially as evidenced by studies on the Mediterranean diet and its role in reducing risks associated with cardiac diseases and neurodegenerative disorders. Clove oil or Eugenol is a dietary polyphenol known to inhibit COX enzymes selectively. However, the potential of the natural product is limited by its reduced half-life and hydrophobic nature. In this report, we talk about a simple nano-encapsulation of Eugenol and its anti-inflammatory abilities.

Methods: Eugenol encapsulated nanocarriers were synthesized using the solvent evaporation method followed by multiple cycles of freeze-thaw. The nanoparticles were then characterized using Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), UV-Vis Spectroscopy and Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS). The encapsulated particles were analyzed for the efficiency of loading and was tested biocompatible.

Results & Discussions: In TEM, AFM and DLS, the particles displayed a size range of 200-300 nm. The particles were observed to be biocompatible in L929 cells and microglia cells. In an *in vitro* pro-inflammatory model of microglia cells, Eugenol encapsulated nanocarriers of two selected concentration switched the majority of cells from a pro-inflammatory state to an anti-inflammatory state without altering the total viability of cells.

Conclusions: Eugenol encapsulated nanocarriers effectively reduces the pro-inflammatory signals in treated cells without changing the viability (1). The particles are biocompatible in both neuronal and non-neuronal cell lines, making it a potential anti-inflammatory molecule from dietary sources.

Keywords: Eugenol, Polyphenol, inflammation, Non-steroid anti-inflammatory drug

References

1. Revi N, Rengan AK. Eugenol-Encapsulated Nanocarriers for Microglial Polarisation: a Promising Therapeutic Application for Neuroprotection. *Bionanoscience* [Internet]. 2020;10(4):1010–7. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12668-020-00789-z>

